

READING LITERACY OF PUPILS OF UZBEKISTAN THE ROLE OF PARTICIPATION IN INTERNATIONAL EXAMINATIONS IN DEVELOPMENT

Jahona Karimova

1st stage master of Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10391928>

Abstract. *The article discusses reading literacy as one of the main parameters of readiness to live and work in modern society, the participation of Uzbek students in the PIRLS international exam, and the results expected from it. It is justified that participation in this exam is an important event in the purposeful development of educational work with young students.*

Keywords: *reading literacy, reading culture, literacy, international study, PIRLS - an international study on the assessment of the quality of reading and text comprehension.*

The idea that a person's reading competence determines his communicative skills is not disputed. Educated (read a lot) It's always fun to talk to someone. It is a popular opinion, a specific trend in pedagogical practice: it is unnecessary to talk too much about the fact that a high level of reading competences in primary school is a guarantee of successful studies in secondary school. Modernization of the education system of Uzbekistan, first primarily aimed at improving the quality of educational services provided by educational institutions. In this case, the effectiveness of the educational process is directly related to the effective, professionally built system of managing the results of external and internal evaluation of the learner. The success of student education depends not only on national examinations, but also on international comparative monitoring studies, independent of the country, of the educational success of learners.

In the concept of development of public education in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, participation of Uzbek students in the PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) international study on the assessment of the quality of reading and understanding of the text is defined. This unique study aims to find out how well children's elementary skills and reading culture are nurtured in the country. In the context of the world, reading culture, literacy is considered as one of the most important parameters of readiness to live in modern society. One of the main conditions for children's success in education - informational competence of students is formed already in primary school, because the quality education received in primary school is considered a solid foundation for all further education. A modern teacher is required to find and use the forms, methods and methods of educational activities that will maximally help in the formation of reading culture of students.

It is of great importance for the elementary school teacher to form the basic skills of working with text in young students: knowing the source of information, searching for an answer to a question that interests him, competently formalizing and presenting the selected material. The acquired knowledge and skills of working with various sources of information will help children to understand information, evaluate its quality, understand and understand its hidden content. The formation of skills related to reading literacy is successful in the conditions of the organic interaction of the components of the educational process, educational activities and additional education. It is also important to purposefully carry out activities related to the expansion and

development of family reading with parents and the public. The participation of Uzbek schools in the upcoming international exam will be another mechanism of targeted work on the development of educational and informational skills of young students, which will not only help the primary school graduate to successfully acquire knowledge at the next level of education. mastering, but also help to form the reading literacy of Uzbek youth.

PIRLS is an international study on the assessment of the quality of reading and text comprehension - a program of the IEA (International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement). The purpose of the PIRLS study is to compare the level of reading comprehension of fourth grade students in different countries of the world, as well as to identify differences in the teaching of reading literacy in national education systems. According to the international glossary prepared by the leading experts of this research, reading literacy is the ability to understand and logically understand various forms of written speech necessary for a person to fully realize himself in life and achieve his goals. With this, an important principle of education policy - for the benefit of man and society - is realized.

The PIRLS study assesses two types of reading that students use more than others in class and outside of school:

- reading to acquire the experience of reading fiction;
- reading in order to acquire and apply information.

During the test, students are offered to read two texts (one artistic and one informative) and 14-16 tasks related to the text. Tasks differ according to the form of the answer: tasks where you have to choose one of the four proposed answers; tasks related to determining the sequence of events; free-form response assignments.

Students are given 80 minutes (divided into two parts of 40 minutes with a break) to complete the work.

In accordance with the conceptual rules of the research, four groups of reading skills are evaluated when reading artistic and informative (scientific-popular) texts:

- find publicly available information;
- forming conclusions;
- interpreting and summarizing information;
- analysis and evaluation of text content, linguistic features and structure.

The assessment of academic and reading success of the participants is carried out in accordance with certain levels based on the acquisition of reading skills of students, accepted by international experts in the field of quality assessment of school education. These levels describe different learning activities according to the level of complexity of students in working with the text proposed in the study. Clear criteria of the levels allow children's results to be statistically divided into separate groups, whose readiness in terms of reading literacy can be characterized using specific tasks that describe a certain level.

PIRLS research aims to solve the following tasks:

- development of objective measures and instruments that reflect global priorities in the field of education;
- comparative assessment of the effectiveness of organizing the educational process in the country;
- to determine the contextual factors that influenced the results of the research;
- receiving scientifically based information recognized by the world community;

- providing research participants with not only country-independent results, but also recommendations for improving education policy, etc.

The object of research is the educational achievements of primary school graduates, because it is in the fourth year of education that all the skills and competencies related to studying and accumulate knowledge. By this time, students should be able to read a variety of texts in both content and format in primary school to the point where they can successfully continue their education. The survey is conducted once in five years. The participation of more than 50 countries of the world in the PIRLS research is determined by the fact that methodological and technical support of the research at the professional organizational level is provided. The universality and reliability of the interpretation of indicators allows for quick compilation and processing of the obtained data. The basis of reading literacy is the formation of reading skills necessary for full work with the text. This is the ability of the reader to find and recreate the necessary information, form conclusions about a certain part of the text, interpret the actions of the main characters, confirm with examples from the text, and do a preliminary analysis of the text structure. The results of the PIRLS study conducted in different countries are widely discussed by the pedagogical community. Mechanisms of monitoring the consequences of the obtained results of students' success will be implemented, educational technologies and requirements for educational achievements of young students will be revised. On the basis of the international test assignments of students' reading literacy conducted within the framework of the research, pedagogical teams and innovative teachers not only evaluate the success of students' educational activities, but also, first of all, the literacy skills and culture as an important factor in the educational success of the country's youth. forms a national base of questions aimed at formation and development. The success formula of students from Japan, Korea, China, Singapore in TIMSS, PISA, PIRLS international exams is their "Perseverance and leadership, knowledge of mathematics, strong physics and, of course, reading skills!" embodied in the slogan. The participation of Uzbek students in international exams within the framework of this research will undoubtedly help to discover new directions in the reform of the educational system and the modernization of educational content, as well as the solution of possible shortcomings.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No. PF-5712 Concept of developing the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030
2. PEARLS complete information about the study. Институт стратегии развития образования Российской академии образования Центр оценки качества образования <http://centeroko.ru>
3. Оценка качества чтения и понимания текста учащимися начальной школы PIRLS. - Астана: НЦОСО, 2013.
4. Оценка влияния родителей на формирование функциональной грамотности школьников. Аналитическое заключение. - Астана: АО «ИАЦ», 2015. - 64 стр.